

The effect of nanoplastic toxicity on the gill tissue of goldfish (*Carassius auratus*)

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Abstract

With the increase in plastic pollution in aquatic ecosystems, nanoplastics have become an emerging pollutant, raising serious environmental concerns. Among these pollutants, polystyrene nanoplastics are of particular importance due to their very small size, high stability, and ability to penetrate biological tissues. The aim of this study is to investigate the effects of polystyrene nanoplastic toxicity on histological changes in goldfish gills, as one of the most sensitive respiratory and ionic regulation organs in fish. In this study, fishes were randomly divided into group control and two treatments with different concentrations (0.5 mg/L and 1 mg/L) of polystyrene nanoplastics and were exposed to these particles for 10, 15, and 20 days. After the end of the exposure period, gill samples were collected and, after fixation and appropriate staining, tissue changes were examined microscopically. The results of the study showed that exposure of fish to polystyrene nanoplastics leads to significant pathological changes in gill tissue, which increase with increasing nanoplastic concentration. In conclusion, it can be said that polystyrene nanoplastics caused structural damage to gill tissue, disrupt respiratory function and ionic balance in fish, and can be considered a serious threat to aquatic animal health and the sustainability of aquatic ecosystems.

Keywords: Nanoplastics; fish; effects; polystyrene; gills.

1. Introduction

In recent years, plastic production has increased around the world, and its waste has been recognized as a threat to marine ecosystem (Eriksen et al., 2013). Because a large number of marine species are affected and harmed by this waste every year (Derraik, 2022) More than 300 million tons of plastic are produced and consumed worldwide annually (Andrady and Neal, 2009). This has led to plastic products being dumped into the ocean in various ways, accounting for 80-60% of marine litter. Assessing the effects of the smallest plastic waste known as nanoparticles (>100 nm) (Hartmann et al., 2015). To fully understand the significance of this emerging threat to the marine environment Plastic particles enter the ocean from urban areas through surface drainage systems, as well as directly from human activities such as fishing, discharges from shipping, and intentional and accidental releases of domestic, agricultural, industrial, and sewage effluents (Andrady, 2011). This has raised significant concerns about nanoplastic pollution and poses a greater threat to marine life than larger plastics because the reduction in size of nanoplastics makes them susceptible to consumption by organisms at the base of the food chain (Browne et al., 2011). In addition, their high surface area relative to their volume makes them carriers of other pollutants such as PAHs, POPs and trace metals (Ag, Cd, Cu, etc.), which tend to cause bioaccumulation and bioamplification (Lusher et al., 2013).

For this reason, marine organisms are sensitive to the consumption of these types of plastics, which have indirect effects, such as accumulation at higher trophic levels. As a result, their consumption by these organisms causes endocrine disruption, toxicological hazards, and the accumulation of organic pollutants in the marine food chain (Cedervall et al., 2012). Nanoplastics pose a more serious threat to the aquatic environment and its ecosystems than other larger plastics (Guerrera et al., 2021).

They are distributed in almost all different types of aquatic habitats, and these substances are available to a wide range of aquatic organisms such as fish (Trevisan et al., 2022). Several factors can affect the bioavailability of nanoplastics in fish (Koelmans et al., 2015). Due to their small size and similarity to food, these particles are consumed by fish either intentionally or accidentally (Abarghouei et al., 2021).

It can cause inflammatory responses, metabolic changes, or even destruction of the fish's immune system (Greven et al., 2016). In addition, many nanoplastics are able to migrate to other organs such as the gills and liver, thereby causing damage to these organs (Mattsson et al., 2017). These substances also affect important biological processes and cause endocrine disruption, which in turn can affect reproduction and cause mutations, and generally have adverse effects on the health of marine organisms in terms of their growth and population (Choi et al., 2018).

Previous studies have shown that nanoplastics are capable of causing oxidative stress, inflammation, metabolic changes, and cellular and tissue damage in various fish species. However, the available information on the histopathological effects of long-term exposures and low concentrations of these particles, especially in goldfish, is still limited and insufficient (Zhang et al., 2022). Also, the exact mechanisms of tissue damage caused by polystyrene nanoplastics on the gill surface have not been fully elucidated (Bhattacharya et al., 2010). Therefore, a better understanding of the effects of these pollutants on fish life, especially at the tissue level, is essential for assessing their environmental risks. In this regard, the present study aimed to investigate histopathological changes in goldfish gill tissue upon exposure to polystyrene nanoplastics at concentrations of 0.5 and 1 mg/L over periods of 10, 15 and 20 days.

The results of this study showed that exposure of goldfish to polystyrene nanoplastics at concentrations of 0.5 and 1 mg/L for periods of 10, 15 and 20 days resulted in significant pathological changes in the tissues. The most important changes observed included hyperplasia, hypertrophy, necrosis, aneurysm, and lamellar fusion in the gill tissue.

The findings of this study can help clarify the dose-dependent and time-dependent effects of nanoplastics on fish health and provide useful and valuable information for assessing the environmental risk of these emerging pollutants.

2. Materials and methods

To conduct this research, 150 specimens of goldfish (Figure1) were purchased in January 2021 from one of the breeding and ornamental ponds in the city of Rasht. Fish samples (weight 5.789 ± 5 grams and total length 6.936 ± 5 centimeters) were transferred to the Marine Biology Laboratory, Faculty of Basic Sciences, University of Guilan. The fry were kept for 12 days in a 250-liter fiberglass pond containing well water with aeration by an air pump, 12 hours in the dark and 12 hours in the light to adapt to laboratory conditions. During this period,

the fish were hand-fed twice a day with commercial goldfish food, and 50% of their water was changed daily. Some physicochemical characteristics of the water were measured daily, and during this period, the fish were maintained at a temperature of 16 ± 2 °C and a pH of 7 ± 2.1 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Experimental setup showing goldfish maintained for 12 days in a 250-L fiberglass tank containing well water under controlled conditions.

Nano polystyrene particles were prepared as an emulsion with a size of 70 nm. Styrene as monomer, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) with a molecular weight of 128,000 g/mol as stabilizer were purchased from Merck, Germany, and benzoyl peroxide as initiator were purchased from Alpha Arizer (USA). Styrene was distilled before use and other chemicals were used as is. Deionized water was used in all experiments. Polystyrene particles were manufactured according to the research of Tohami et al. (2016) and Shoshani et al. (2017).

According to these methods, 1-3% by weight of initiator (benzoyl peroxide), 1-4% by weight of stabilizer (polyvinyl alcohol) was selected and the stirring speed was set to 550-750 rpm. The polymerization was carried out in a 1-liter three-neck reactor equipped with an addition funnel (dropwise addition of styrene monomer), a condenser, and a thermometer. In the reaction vessel, 400 ml of distilled water, initiator, and stabilizer were added, and nitrogen gas was passed through for 20 minutes to remove dissolved oxygen. Then, the temperature was raised to 90°C and, while stirring, styrene was gradually added dropwise over a period of half an hour, and the polymerization reaction continued for 8 hours. For the semi-chronic experiment, concentrations of 0.5 and 1 mg/l in water were considered for nano-polystyrene, and according to the desired concentrations, 120 goldfish were examined in three treatments (two single nano-polystyrene treatments, control treatment) for 10, 15, and 20 days in triplicate.

To determine the concentrations of nano-polystyrene under semi-chronic experiment conditions, initial experiments were first conducted with different concentrations of nano-polystyrene. Given that fish did not show mortality at the concentrations tested within 96 hours. The results of the initial experiments and based on previous studies (Estrala et al., 2021; Abarghouei et al., 2021).

The desired concentrations were considered for individual nanopolystyrene treatments. During this period, 10, 15, and 20 days, the fry were fed three percent of their weight every other day, and the tank water was siphoned 50 percent every two days. The pollutant concentrations were calculated again and added to the tank water, and the desired volume was reached with aerated and dechlorinated city water. Due to the biometry, the weight of the goldfish was measured with a digital scale with an accuracy of 0.01 grams, and the length of the goldfish was checked at the beginning and end of the experiment. In order to reduce stress and empty the digestive system, feeding was stopped 48 hours before sampling and the fish were anesthetized with water and ice (Figure 2) after anesthesia, the gills were removed using a razor blade and then the gill tissue was fixed in 10% formalin for histological studies.

Then, the samples of the dehydration stages were subjected to different alcohol levels, then clarified with the organic solvent xylene and embedded with paraffin. Very thin sections of the tissue with a diameter of 5 microns were prepared using a microtome (Leica RM2255) and made into slides. Staining was performed using the standard hematoxylin-eosin (H&E) method.

Figure 2. Fish anesthesia induced by water and ice immersion.

3. Gill tissue pathology results

In the present study, the control treatment of gill tissue showed mild side effects such as hyperplasia. Different polystyrene nanoplastic treatments in the gill tissue of goldfish showed effects such as hyperplasia, edema, and epithelial detachment in all exposed samples with different intensities. Also, some complications such as hypertrophy and increased volume of chondrocyte nuclei, aneurysm, lamella fusion, and necrosis were observed in some treatments, especially those with longer durations (Figure 3) and (table1).

Table 1. This table shows various side effects over different time periods

Treatment and days Complications	Control	0.5 mg/l Np-PS in 10 days	1 mg/l Np-PS in 10 days	0.5 mg/l Np-PS in 15 days	1 mg/l Np-PS in 15 days	1mg/l Np-PS in 20 days
Hyperplasia	+	++	+	+++	+++	+++
Epithelium detachment	-	+	+	++	+++	+++
Adem	-	+	+	++	+++	+++
Hypertrophy and increased volume of chondrocyte nuclei	-	-	-	-	+	++
Aneurysm	-	-	-	++	++	++
Lamella fusion	-	-	-	-	+	+++
Necrosis	-	-	-	-	+	+++

- No complications observed: No significant pathological changes or histological abnormalities were observed. The structure of the gills was completely normal, with the primary and secondary lamellae arranged in a regular and uniform manner. The gill epithelium was healthy, thin, and without signs of hyperplasia or hypertrophy.

+ Mild complication: Fish exposed to polystyrene nanoplastics at a concentration of 0.5 mg/L for 10 days showed mild pathological changes in gill tissue. These changes included edema, mild epithelial hyperplasia, and localized detachment of the epithelium from the secondary lamella.

++Moderate complication: Exposure of fish to polystyrene nanoplastics at a concentration of 0.5 mg/L for 15 days resulted in moderate pathological lesions in gill tissue. These changes included epithelial hyperplasia, epithelial lifting, edema, and aneurysm.

+++Severe complication: Exposure of fish to polystyrene nanoplastics at a concentration of 1 mg/L for 15 and 20 days resulted in severe pathological lesions in the gill tissue. These changes included severe epithelial hyperplasia, epithelial detachment, edema, and hyperplasia. During the 20-day exposure period, more advanced lesions were also observed, including lamellar fusion and tissue necrosis.

Figure 3. This figure represents various side effects.

The effect of single nanoplastics on the gill tissue of juvenile goldfish : A-Control treatment B-Polystyrene nanoplastic treatment at a concentration of 0.5 mg/liter for 10 days C- Polystyrene nanoplastic treatment at a concentration of 1 mg/L individually for 10 days D- Nanoplastic treatment at a concentration of 0.5 mg/liter for 15 days E- Polystyrene nanoplastic treatment at a concentration of 1 mg/liter/liter for 15 days F-

Polystyrene nanoplastic treatment at a concentration of 0.5 mg/liter for 20 days G- Polystyrene nanoplastic treatment at a concentration of 1 mg/liter for 20 days (F) Filament, (L) Lamella, (N) Necrosis, (HPC) Hypertrophy and increased red blood cell volume, (DY) Epithelial detachment, (OE) Edema, (FU) Lamella fusion (HP) Hyperplasia, (AN) Aneurysm.

4. Discussion

Gills are the first target of water pollutants due to their constant contact with the external environment. Due to its function, location, and blood supply, it is most closely associated with the detoxification and biotransformation process and is one of the organs most affected by pollutants in water (Hadi and Alwan, 2012). Due to the short diffusion distance and large surface area between blood and water, the gills are primarily affected by pollutants (Carvalho et al., 2020). In general, gill cells respond rapidly to several chemicals to manage tissue damage or physiological disorders (Pacchierotti et al., 2017). Chemicals may negatively impact overall gill function, enhance fish sensitivity to toxic compounds, and potentially cause fish gill destruction (Özaslan et al., 2017).

Several studies have been conducted on the histological changes that occur in gill tissue in the presence of environmental pollutants. Histological studies are a useful indicator for assessing damage caused by nanomaterials. It seems that high concentrations of these pollutants cause the loss of adhesion between epithelial cells and the underlying columnar cell system, which disrupts respiration and health in fish.

One of the adverse effects of chemicals on fish gills is disruption of ion and gas exchange. Increased cell numbers in gill tissue due to exposure to pollutants can cause respiratory restriction. It is possible that gill hyperplasia may be caused by the presence and influence of an irritant pollutant in the water (Humphrey et al., 2010). In addition to respiratory distress, this condition increases the distance between blood and oxygen, which can lead to tissue hypoxia (Lappivaara et al., 1995).

Another tissue change affected by pollutants is epithelial detachment, which is caused by severe edema. Edema, along with detachment of the lamellar epithelium, serves as a defense mechanism, because epithelial detachment increases the distance between water pollutants and the bloodstream (Arellano et al., 1999). Hyperemia is a defense mechanism that prevents the entry of pollutants that cause complications in the gill tissue (Waheed et al., 2025). One of the causes of hyperemia is the dilation of blood vessels and rapid blood flow into the gill filaments, which reduces the interlamellar space and, as a result, reduces the vulnerability of the gills to the entry of pollutants through the epithelium (Eghdami et al., 2014).

Abnormal proliferation of cells around the lamellae and increased hyperplasia cause a decrease in the space between the lamellae, resulting in adhesion and ultimately fusion in the gill tissue (Lappivaara et al., 1995). In the present study, after fish were exposed to the pollutant, it showed lamellar fusion, which may be due to impaired permeability. Therefore, lamellar fusion due to exposure of fish to polystyrene nanoplastics can reduce blood oxygen levels in fish, causing systemic oxygen deficiency and hypoxia (Bilberg et al., 2010). Also, the fusion of lamellae reduces the gill surface area and reduces the contact between gill epithelial cells and toxic substances, as well as reducing ion and gas exchange between secondary lamellae, affecting fish health (Haghighat et al., 2021). Therefore, it seems that the changes in goldfish after exposure to individual nanoplastics are a physiological response that the fish has developed to prevent these types of pollutants from entering their bodies and preventing damage (da Cruz da Cruz et al., 2015). Previous studies have shown similar effects of these pollutants on fish gill tissue, including studies that have shown that exposure to plastic particles such as microplastics can cause nutritional or energy problems in fish and can affect the basic structures of cell membranes.

This phenomenon causes disruption of the ability to regulate osmosis following gill damage (Özaslan et al., 2017). Studies have shown that smaller nanoplastic particles (particles less than 100 nm) are more easily internalized into cells by endocytosis compared to larger microplastics and nanoplastics (Atugoda et al., 2022). Nanoplastics cause intracellular damage to cytoplasmic organelles, mainly mitochondria (Lee et al., 2019). In the present study, changes in the gill tissue of goldfish were more severe when exposed to nanoplastics over a longer period of time.

5. Conclusion

The results of histological examinations showed that no significant pathological changes were observed in the control group. The structure of the gills was completely normal and the gill epithelium was healthy and without signs of hyperplasia or hypertrophy. Fish exposed to polystyrene nanoplastics at a concentration of 0.5 mg/L

for 10 days showed mild pathological changes in gill tissue. Fish exposed to polystyrene Nano plastics at a concentration of 0.5 mg/L for 15 days developed moderate pathological lesions in gill tissue. Exposure of fish to polystyrene nanoplastics at a concentration of 1 mg/L for 15 and 20 days resulted in severe pathological lesions in the gill tissue. These changes included severe epithelial hyperplasia, extensive epithelial detachment, severe edema, and in more advanced stages, lamellar fusion and necrosis.

6. Suggestions

According to the results of this study, significant changes in the gill tissue of fish exposed to polystyrene nanoplastics are suggested:

1- Future research should focus on understanding the precise molecular and cellular mechanisms of the toxicity of these particles.

2- It is recommended to investigate the effects of chronic exposure to lower concentrations of nanoplastics over a longer period of time.

3- It is essential to assess the effects of nanoplastics on other vital organs, including the liver, intestine, and kidney, in order to more comprehensively understand systemic toxicity.

4- It is recommended to conduct studies on different species of freshwater and marine fish to generalize the results.

5- Due to the occurrence of textural changes at higher concentrations, determining the permissible limits of nanoplastics in water resources should be considered by relevant institutions.

6- It is essential to adopt effective management strategies to reduce and prevent the entry of nanoplastics into aquatic ecosystems, including improving plastic waste management.

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